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*Teaching Engineers on Innovation and Creativity
Innovation, Creativity and User Oriented Product Development in Engineering
Education*

Y. Jeanrenaud¹

Research Assistant for Gender Studies in Science and Engineering
Technical University
of Munich (TUM), Gender Studies in Science and Engineering
Munich, Germany
E-mail: yes.jeanrenaud@tum.de

S. Ihsen

Professor for Gender Studies in Science and Engineering
Technical University of Munich (TUM), Gender Studies in Science and Engineering
Munich, Germany
E-mail: ihsen@tum.de

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INTRODUCTION

An interdisciplinary master class called “Customer needs meet the technical market” is now thought at Technical University of Munich for more than seven years in the study programmes of industrial engineering as well as electrical engineering and information technology. It focusses on aspects of product development and the inclusion of end users’ perspective into the innovation and product development process [1]. Hence, it highlights the importance of diversity and gender aspects in science and product engineering throughout all stages of technological products’ innovation process from the idea up to the market launch. The goal of this interdisciplinary class is to make students aware of different target groups in potential

¹ Corresponding Author

markets and their background [2, 3]. It introduces different methods of user integration, e.g. market research and open innovation on the background of sociological as well as gender and diversity studies theories and frameworks. In addition, the strategy of Diversity Management is discussed and its relevance for product engineering and marketing using the example of mixed teams [2]. Students' deep understanding of product engineering, design and product innovation process management tools is needed which is worked out in a problem-based-learning framework [4]. Furthermore, the importance of creativity and creative processes [5] for innovation are highlighted and several techniques for fostering creativity in product engineering processes are introduced and practised exemplarily.

This paper would like to discuss in detail the didactical goals, methods and exercises used in the master class on innovation in product engineering at Technical University of Munich and therefore contribute to further development of engineering education regarding teaching gender and diversity with their links to creativity and innovation in engineering.

1 RATIONALE

In our changing world of work, opportunities to up skill are increasingly important. Digitalisation [6] and Industry 4.0 [7] are changing not only the landscape of work-life [6, 8] but also of university education across all disciplines [9]. Therefore, it is crucial, maybe even more than ever before, to look out of the box when it comes to engineering education. Since 2005, hence for more than a decade now at Technical University of Munich, the professorship of Gender Studies in Science and Engineering teaches engineering students with social science and gender studies methods, also to foster gender sensitive didactics and educate on the impact of gender and diversity in engineering education [9]. In order to explain this, we need to go back in time a bit:

When university didactics developed slowly after years of virtually a standstill in Germany in the 1960s, criticism on the prevailing scientific system and approaches to university and study reform were voiced from within the natural and engineering sciences from the very beginning, too. One might have thought critique would have been the domain of humanities and social sciences. These critics might have been perceived predominant, but this might be a deceptive view [10]. Together with the Aachen physicist Brigitte Eckstein, an initially small group of academic faculty members at various locations of technical colleges and universities in Germany addressed the connection between active learning and critical thinking for the training of future generations of engineers. Via their scientific contacts to the United States of America, and especially to the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), they brought the ways of thinking of Ruth Cohn (especially thematic interaction [11]), Kurt Lewin (group dynamics, inter alia [12]) and David A. Kolb (learning style inventory [13]) into their concepts for a changed engineering education [14].

Ever since the 1960s, the development of didactics towards critical thinking and active learning processes in engineering education, per contra among other things to traditionally predominant ex-cathedra lectures, evolved and is currently also part of concepts of inclusive learning environments [15, 16] to change the identities of future engineering professionals [17].

This historical foundation is crucial for our understanding of engineering education as one branch of higher education didactics [18]. By this, engineering education deals with not only the specific teaching, learning and content of engineering, but as well with the tasks of engineers in professional practice and society. Its goals therefore are expanded from sole

transfer of technical knowledge and skills to a broader view of engineering as a profession for and with society as a whole which is bound to include all students in a class [16] regardless their major study programme or background.

In the interdisciplinary master class “Customer needs meet the technical market” discussed in this paper as an example, we seek to push engineering students of the study programmes of industrial engineering as well as electrical engineering and information technology to the limits of their comfort zones and provoke unusual questions which they are usually not confronted with during their study programmes. By doing so, our didactical goal is to teach them gender sensitivity, creativity and innovation for their future careers and raise awareness and responsibility on various levels on among these future engineers.

2 SCOPE

The interdisciplinary course “Customer needs meet the technical market” started in winter semester 2010/11 for the international study programme of industrial engineering as a master class in the study field of compulsory optional subjects. By this, the module became part of an international study programme called “Consumer affairs”. Ever since it reoccurs in every winter semester. It was modulated as one of two classes for the module “Consumer Psychology & Gender Studies” with a total of 6 ECTS [19], the course itself is worth two semester periods per week and 3 ECTS, therefore half of the full module. Furthermore, it was modulated as an elective subject in the master study programme of electrical engineering and information technology with two semester periods per week and 3 ECTS as well. By this design, the target group for this course usually consists largely of consumer affairs students with very heterogeneous and diverse backgrounds, also because of the international joint degree master programme that is implemented within the consumer affairs study programme. Nonetheless, a hand full of electrical engineering students and some from other study programmes such as mechanical engineering or architecture join the courses, too. This combination of elective subject-students and compulsory optional subject-students from various study programmes, different bachelor’s degrees and background requires teaching to be more deliberated. Therefore, an inclusive learning environment [15] ought to be fostered.

The initial course concept was rather traditionally, for a social sciences class at least, conceptualised with twelve different topics on the subject of the course presented by the students in small groups. These twelve group-presentations covered various topics and aimed at covering the course topic in a narrowing manner. For example, these included: “The Identification of target-groups”, “Cars for women”, “Handbags for men and mobile phones for elderly persons: The diversity-perspective in product development”, “Innovation processes, innovation dimensions and innovation types”, “Open innovation – user integration in innovation processes”, “Lead User Methodology” and “Creativity – the key to innovation”.

The presentations were grouped into four topics:

1. Customer needs – what for?
2. Innovation and Creativity
3. Diversity-Management
4. Innovation-Management

For each of these topics, a block date was aligned consisting of six to eight course hours including breaks. By this model, students were able to better coordinate this class with their already fully packed study programme schedule.

The class is scheduled only for winter semesters and from year to year it is constantly developed further and adapted to tweak its methodology and content based on new insights from science and didactics as well as on student's formalised feedback through evaluation sheets and informal oral feedback at the end of the last course day.

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Within the course "Customer needs meet the technical market", problem-based-learning [4] is the main didactical methodology to teach profound as well as first-stage insights for engineering students outside of their subject area. Many topics, especially creativity and innovation processes are not taught by presentations but also by short exercises of twenty to forty-five minutes duration in small groups between three and six students. For example, to think about methods of fostering creativity, a short exercise where chains of ideas ignited by pictures licensed under creative commons (e.g. cc-by [20]) are carried out in class. A collection of thirty pictures, one example shown below in *Fig. 1* are printed and handed out to student groups three to six students, depending on the number of students participating in the course. These groups thereafter loosely associate thoughts and ideas that emerge from looking at these pictures, preferably without describing their content in explicitly and note them down.

Fig. 1. Cornfield Kid, cc-by-2.0 by Sam Cockman at flickr [21]

After fifteen to twenty minutes, each group presents their result to the class while the corresponding pictures are shown via LCD projection.

In order to look at the process of innovation management and innovation processes, basically in enterprises, we introduced a short idea competition in the class. Students are grouped together by three to five persons and have to come up with a creative idea for a new technological product within a given constraints, e.g. a wristwatch. After two weeks, the groups present their ideas to all participating students and the lecturers and also commit one group member to a selection committee. This jury thereafter assesses the ideas presented

by all groups before, whereas each jury member abstains from voting in case of own group involvement in order to avoid biases. This, but just as a short excursus, is implemented to exercise democratic methods, processes and measurements in engineering education [22]. After the assessment, a small prize, usually a card box full of sweets and candy, is given to the winning team as an award, which they frequently share thereafter with all students of the class.

With the commencement of winter semester 2015/16, the course was slightly revised, on basis of the responses and needs of students in the preceding years. Even though these changes were not implemented abrupt, the winter semester 2015/16 constitutes a milestone. Notably the e-learning concept of blended learning [23] was successfully applied, whereas e-learning and traditional learning settings in class were combined. As e-learning platform, a Moodle installation at Technical University of Munich is used [24, 25]. On Moodle, not only the course's literature and information is made available but also the students publish their works and findings during the course.

Starting from the winter semester 2017/18, the blended learning was optimised and the course schedule was adapted to the student's increasingly full study programme schedules. Hence, the master course "Customer needs meet the technical market" now consists of five fortnightly parts composed of merely two topics, whereas the course dates were limited to 3.5 hours. The topics of these five half-days were:

1. Customer needs – what for?
2. The Role of Gender and Diversity in Marketing
3. Innovation and Creativity
4. Managing Creativity
5. Reflection

Furthermore, group presentation of the texts were buried in favour of an elevator pitch-method. For these, all students have to read through the literature on the two topics of the corresponding day. This literature consists of six to eight ready-made texts from social science, gender and diversity studies and product development as well as from other disciplines and is about 80 pages in total. In class, two students thereafter are randomly chosen and assigned to a three-minute talk on the texts read on one and another subject of the day. For these strictly three minutes, the students ought not to summarize the text that (should) have been read (and preferably understood) by all participants, but they highlight the most important aspects, key take-homes and surprises or astonishments of the literature given to them. By this, the student assigned to the topic, e.g. "Integration of diversity aspects in science", does not only reproduce knowledge from the literature for the class orally, but also gives insights into their interpretation and prioritisation. Afterwards, a discussion in class follows in order to broaden and elaborate the topic again.

For the blended learning aspect, in winter semester 2017/18, we assigned the students for the first time to each produce a written summary of each of the five course dates and upload to Moodle within seven days from each course day. These half-pagers were made available to all students of the class afterwards within the Moodle course for the corresponding semester and therefore everyone could benefit from the summaries written and insights gained by the other participants of the class. The grading of these papers also takes place in Moodle. In this semester, for the first time the course was held by two lecturers.

To further develop and adapt the course “Customer needs meet the technical market” we use evaluation forms and feedback talks with students.

Fig. 2. Course evaluation results summarised

As shown in Fig. 2 above, the evaluation forms main part consists of four categories:

1. Content and skills (blue, upper left quadrant)
2. Presentation (if required) (orange, lower left quadrant)
3. Paper (if required) (gray, upper right quadrant)
4. Lecturer and learning environment (yellow, lower right quadrant)

Questions included here are for example “The content meets my expectations.”, “There are enough opportunities to practice the presentation.” or “The lecturer was well prepared”, to name a few. Fig. 2 includes not only the average values over the various semesters (continuous lines) for these four categories and their standard deviations (opaque zones) in each quadrant, but also the number of evaluation forms returned (n). Therefore, the y-axis on the right-hand side represents the scales of n whereas the y-axis on the left-hand side represents the values of responses on a Likert scale (1 to 5, [26]). The x-axis represents the corresponding winter semesters from winter semester 10/11 to winter semester 17/18. The value of n obviously is fluctuating heavily and depending on the size of the course’s audience in each semester, too. Furthermore it has to be noted that the evaluation was until winter semester 2014/15 consisting of 22 questions, whereas four counted in for content (1), two for both presentation (2) and paper (3) and three for lecturer (4). These questions were expanded faculty-wide in winter semester 2015/16 to seven questions on content (1) and five on lecturer(s) (4). Other question groups were also altered. In addition, the sequence of the scale was inverted from 1 for “disagree completely” to 5 for “agree completely”, but for

Fig. 2, we reversed those back and ditched the new question to have more or less comparable results. Because standardised feedback in evaluation forms bears bias to some extent, we also include informal oral evaluation rounds, which give us valuable insights and feedback.

4 FINDINGS

Positive evaluations dominated the feedback ever since the course “Customer needs meet the technical market” was implemented in winter semester 2010/11, particularly the informal oral feedback. Especially highlighted were the numerous exercises and the problem-based-learning approach which seem to be, even in winter semester 2017/18, more or less uncommon and noteworthy to the students learning experience at Technical University of Munich and elsewhere [27]. Nonetheless, the students struggled with a lack of lecture-oriented teaching they perceived. Some students all of the years voiced feedback whereas they wished to have more of an ex-cathedra teaching and also some of the topics were perceived to be dealt with more fundamentally than students would have expected. Especially the perception of the depth of the topics covered changed after the blended learning concept was introduced and after group presentations were ditched in favour of elevator pitches as teaching and learning success measurement methods. It seems, students were more unhappy with presentation of topics by their ilk due to the level of complexity some student broke down the knowledge. Even though this might be due to the interdisciplinary and internationality of the study programme, it is a welcomed side effect of the development undertaken in this course over the years.

Furthermore, the course led to multiple master theses written at the professorship, e.g. on “Gender Differences in Attracting and Recruiting Candidates for STEM Positions via Social Media Channels”.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We could show, by using the example of the course “Customer needs meet the technical market”, how a systematically approach of introducing critical thinking and active learning in engineering education might look like. It showed that by this, we were able to work towards an inclusive learning environment [15] and foster a broader view of technology impact and engineering core curricular content among students of diverse study programmes and backgrounds. By doing so, it is possible to further development of engineering education regarding teaching gender, diversity with their links to creativity and innovation.

Further research is nonetheless foreseen on didactics and methods for undergraduate students and non-traditional learning environments, e.g. massive open online courses (MOOCs), where only first appraisals concerning gender and diversity were conducted so far [28] and not much sustainable research is available yet on didactics towards critical thinking and active learning.

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